

A Reductive Theory of Cause and Intervention

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This note develops a reductive INUS-style semantics and shows how finite acyclic Pearl-style intervention models can be embedded in it. It is posted as an archival record of work originally written circa 2013. This archival version is available at doi:10.5281/zenodo.20370216.

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Abstract

The interventionist theory proposed by Pearl is the most broadly applied theory of cause in recent times. However, it suffers from a fundamental limitation: it does not provide a *reductive* definition of cause. This has wide ranging consequences since it places fundamental limits on our ability to learn causal knowledge and reason with it. I propose a solution to this problem. I prove that a modification of the INUS theory, a reductive theory of cause introduced in the philosophy literature by Mackie, subsumes that of Pearl's. This result allows us to view INUS as a reductive basis for Pearl's theory. I then show how we can use the connection between INUS and Pearl's theory to defend against some outstanding objections to the INUS theory. Finally, I describe some important questions that are now tractable with a reductive definition for cause.

1 Introduction

In recent years, a theory of cause (hereafter referred to as CP, for Causation-Pearl) advanced by Pearl [1], [2] along with complementary work done by Spirtes et al. [3] has generated a lot of interest. It incorporates many results relevant to learning causal quantities from data that are now part of the standard toolkit of a steadily growing set of researchers. It is the widely used model of causation in cognitive psychology and related fields.

Despite its broad application, CP suffers from a critical limitation. It does not provide a *reductive* definition of cause, that is, it does not define cause in strictly simpler terms. CP explains cause in terms of interventions, but interventions are themselves causal. Pearl does not provide an explicit definition for interventions, but their causal nature is readily apparent from the many examples he gives in [2]. A detailed investigation of interventions is also given by Woodward in [4] where he

makes their causal content explicit (see [5] for a summary). He defines I as being an intervention for X only if, among other things, I causes X . This clearly results in a non-reductive account of cause.

The absence of a reductive definition is a profound limitation. We cannot claim to have answered the basic question, “what is cause?”, without it. It means that we cannot develop a deductive system that is *complete* and includes both causal and non-causal statements of interest. This limitation affects all the areas where we apply the theory—from the design of artificial agents that learn and reason causally, to understanding of how our brains use causal knowledge, to scientists learning causal relationships from data.

In this paper, I argue for a theory that is reductive and subsumes CP, and can therefore be viewed as the reductive generalization of it. The theory I propose is a modification of the INUS theory. The INUS theory was introduced in the philosophy literature by Mackie in [6], and further developed in [7]. It originates in the work done by Hume [8], [9] and Mill [10]. The INUS theory has so far been viewed as an alternative to CP. It is not known that INUS subsumes CP. The central result of the paper is a proof of this, along with a model theoretic formalization of the INUS theory.

The fact that INUS subsumes CP, along with being reductive, is a powerful argument for its adoption. Connecting INUS to CP aligns INUS with a theory of demonstrated utility and intuitive appeal. The connection to CP also helps respond to some objections (see Baumgartner [11] for some examples) against the INUS theory. It allows us to utilize the powerful machinery of interventions to resolve these issues. I provide an example of this approach by responding to the well-known *Manchester-Factory-Hooters* example that is one of the significant challenges to INUS.

The reductive theory also gives us a path to explore many interesting questions that were previously intractable. I describe some of these in the section on future work.

2 Introduction to CP

In CP, the analysis of a causal system starts with a determination of a set of properties, or variables, for that system, and a specification of the values that those variables can take.¹ The causal relations are then expressed as a set of functions. Each function is understood as describing the causal dependency of one property on others.

Consider for example a system of two light bulbs controlled by a switch. Let us analyze the system through three variables, S for the state of the switch, and B_1 and B_2 for the state of the bulbs. Let S , B_1 , and B_2 , take on values from the set $\{1, 0\}$.

A full specification of the system involves defining the functions, specifying which functions correspond to which property, and finally specifying the correspondence between properties and the parameters for each of the functions. Some conventions will allow us to do this with brevity. I will refer to the function that specifies the causal dependency of a variable X as f_X . I will use the lowercase of the property names for parameter variables that correspond to that property. So $f_X(y, z) = y + z$ specifies that the property X is causally dependent on property Y and Z and that the function that defines the relation is the addition function.

In the simple system described above, the causal relations consist of two functions and are described by the simple equations $f_{B_1}(s) = s$ and $f_{B_2}(s) = s$. By this we claim that the state of the bulbs are caused by the state of the switch. When the switch is on it causes the bulbs to glow, and when it is off it causes the bulbs to be dark.

The content of these causal claims according to CP can be expressed in three parts. First, it tells us that there is a deterministic relationship between the variables. When the switch is on

¹CP actually consists of two compatible theories—*causal Bayesian networks* and *structural equation models*. Structural equation models are strictly more expressive however, and are what I refer to as CP.

($S = 1$), the bulbs will glow ($B_1 = B_2 = 1$), for example. Second, it tells us that causes precede effects in time, so B_1 follows S temporally.

Finally, it tells us how the system responds to *interventions*. What happens, for example, if bulb 1 is broken? CP proposes that the causal relationship is modular, that is, it is unaffected by interventions to other variables. If bulb 1 is broken, only the causal relationships that govern the way B_1 is set are changed, so bulb 1 will be dark, but bulb 2 remains responsive to the state of the switch. The system after the intervention can therefore be represented by changing just the function corresponding to the variable intervened upon.

It is clear from this example that an intervention is a causal entity. Intuitively, what seems to characterize an intervention is that it is a causal mechanism outside the scope of what is being modeled. This intuition will be formalized as part of the proof that INUS subsumes CP.

3 Introduction to INUS

Mackie defines a cause as being *at least an Insufficient but Necessary part of an Unnecessary but Sufficient (INUS) set of conditions* for an effect. This definition is analytically convoluted and can be given a much simpler characterization that I will use instead. A cause is an element of a *minimally sufficient set*² of conditions for the effect. A minimally sufficient set of conditions is a set of conditions such that any proper subset of it is no longer sufficient.

Let us consider the example Mackie uses to motivate his definition. Consider a short circuit that causes a house to catch fire. The short circuit is not a necessary condition for the fire. There are many other reasons why a house can catch fire—a lit cigarette, a gas leak, a misplaced candle, and so on. The short circuit is also not by itself a sufficient condition for the fire. The presence of oxygen, flammable materials, and surely many other conditions, also need to hold. What can be said about the short circuit however is that it is *part of a set of conditions that are sufficient* for the house to catch fire. The short circuit along with the presence of oxygen, flammable materials, and so on, are sufficient for the house to catch fire. We can further say that without the short circuit, the set of conditions is not sufficient to start the fire. What this amounts to is that the short circuit is a part of a *minimally sufficient set* of conditions for the house to catch fire.

To complete his definition, Mackie defines what he means by sufficient. He proposes that X is sufficient for Y when *for all instances* where X is true, Y is also true. To say that short circuits cause house fires is therefore to say that a short circuit is part of a minimal set of conditions, such that for all instances where the set of conditions are true, the fire always occurs.

Under this interpretation of sufficiency, the requirement that cause is a minimally sufficient set for an effect is extremely strong, perhaps too strong. It requires that the set of conditions be followed by the effect for every instance of the system in the universe, at any time the cause conditions are met, and regardless of any other properties. It is difficult to find such strict regularity in the world. Mackie allows for a way in which to make weaker causal statements by introducing causal fields. A causal field is a proposition that restricts the quantification introduced by sufficiency to range over only those situations where the causal field is true. For example, what causes of influenza in the causal field of humans, is a more general question than what causes influenza in the causal field of humans older than 60 years.

This definition given by Mackie is clearly reductive. Cause is defined in terms of sufficiency, which is defined in terms of universal quantification, which has a clearly non-causal interpretation.

²This terminology is used by Mackie himself and is based on Marc-Wogau [12].

4 Formalization

In this section I present a formalization of the INUS theory along with some modifications. I will refer to the formalized variation as CM (for Causation-Mackie). The formal system that I present is in the form of a logic. A logic provides a meaning, or *semantics*, to sentences in a language by defining a *truth* relation. The truth relation defines what *models* a sentence is true in. The language contains sentences that make causal claims. Models are simplifications of universes. The truth relation therefore defines what universe (after simplification) a causal sentence is true in.

When introducing a logic, some ambiguities can arise in descriptions. We will be tempted to use the same notation for terms that refer to elements of the language we are defining, such as symbols and sentences, and terms that refer to elements in the model, such as numbers and functions. For example, we will want to talk about both a symbol for the number 0 and the number 0 itself. To disambiguate, I will underline terms that refer to symbols or sentences. So $\underline{0}$ is a symbol, but 0 is a number. Similarly, $\underline{P(x) = x + 1}$ is a sentence, but $P(x) = x + 1$ is a function.

4.1 Model

A model contains a set of homogenous *systems*. A system is an interacting group of entities, for example, the parts of a clock, a human body, etc. Systems are understood through their *properties*, which are allowed to change with time. Time is discrete and has a beginning.³ It is convenient therefore to represent time as natural numbers. Properties are functions that assign, to each system and point in time, a value. The value is an element of another set—the range of the property.

Before we introduce a model formally, we first look at the notion of a *signature*. When considering a logical system we would like to fix some aspects of it, such as the names of properties, but still want a more general framework that is independent of these particular choices. This is achieved by parametrizing the components of the logic by a signature. The signature compartmentalizes the contextual parts of the logic and can be replaced for different contexts.

A **signature** \mathbb{S} is a tuple $\langle \mathcal{P}, \{\mathcal{C}_{\underline{P}} : \underline{P} \in \mathcal{P}\} \rangle$ where \mathcal{P} and $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{P}}$ are sets of *symbols*. The elements in \mathcal{P} are symbols for properties. The elements in $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{P}}$ are constant symbols that refer to values in the range of the property referred to by \underline{P} . We are now ready to define a model formally.

A **model** \mathbb{U} **over a signature** \mathbb{S} is a tuple $\mathbb{U} = \langle \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{V}_{\underline{P}} : \underline{P} \in \mathcal{P}\} \rangle$, where:

1. \mathcal{U} is a set of systems.
2. \mathcal{R} is a function that assigns to every element $\underline{P} \in \mathcal{P}$ a set. The set $\mathcal{R}(\underline{P})$ is the range of the property referred to by \underline{P} .
3. \mathcal{F} is a function that assigns to every element $\underline{P} \in \mathcal{P}$ a function from $(\mathcal{U}, \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \mathcal{R}(\underline{P})$, where \mathbb{N} is the set of natural numbers. The function $\mathcal{F}(\underline{P})$ is the actual property referred to by \underline{P} in the model \mathbb{U} . For convenience, I will sometimes use P as shorthand for $\mathcal{F}(\underline{P})$.
4. $\mathcal{V}_{\underline{P}}$ is a function that assigns to every constant $\underline{c}_P \in \mathcal{C}_{\underline{P}}$ a value in $\mathcal{R}(\underline{P})$. The value $\mathcal{V}_{\underline{P}}(\underline{c}_P)$ is the one referred to by the constant \underline{c}_P in the model \mathbb{U} .

4.2 Language

The language introduced here is intentionally minimal. It is intended to be the simplest possible language for expressing causal relations. As with models, the language is defined over a signature

³This is a severely simplistic view of time. It is sufficient however to derive many interesting results. A more realistic model of time will also be investigated in future papers.

\mathbb{S} . A language is a set of sentences. A sentence is a sequence of symbols. Symbols that make up a sentence come from \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{C}_P defined in the signature, along with some additional symbols. In particular, we will have symbols for logical connectives (\wedge and \neg ⁴), a symbol for equality (\equiv), a symbol for the cause relation (*causes*), and finally symbols for parenthesis ($($ and $)$). Most sentences will be a meaningless sequence of symbols. We will restrict our consideration to only a specific subset of sentences called *well-formed sentences* defined by the following production rules. The definition is over a signature \mathbb{S} .

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Atomic Property Formula (APF)} &:= \underline{P = c_P} && \text{where } \underline{P} \in \mathcal{P}, \text{ and } \underline{c_P} \in \mathcal{C}_P \\
\text{Property Formula (PF)} &:= \underline{APF} \mid \underline{(PF \wedge PF)} \mid \underline{(\neg PF)} \\
\text{Unqualified Causal Formula (UCF)} &:= \underline{(APF, \dots, APF) \text{ causes } (APF, \dots, APF)} \\
\text{Qualified Causal Formula (QCF)} &:= \underline{(PF) \implies UCF} \\
\text{Well Formed Sentence (WFS)} &:= \underline{UCF} \mid \underline{QCF}
\end{aligned}$$

The **language \mathbb{L} over signature \mathbb{S}** is the set of all well-formed sentences over \mathbb{S} .

The atomic property formula is the equivalent of what Mackie calls “conditions”. The short circuit, inactive sprinklers, presence of flammable materials, the house catching fire, etc., from Mackie’s example can be translated into the formal language to atomic property formulas such as *Short Circuit = 1*, *Flammables = 1*, *Fire = 1* etc.

Unqualified type causal formulas are the statements that connect the atomic property formulas (the conditions) into causal claims. An example of this is the statement (*Short Circuit = 1, Flammables = 1 causes Fire = 1*).

Qualified type causal formulas are causal formulas involving a causal field. The $\underline{\gamma}$ in the qualified type causal formula $\underline{\gamma \implies \alpha}$ is the causal field.

The structure of the causal statement indicates the first departure of CM from INUS. In CM, I take cause to be a sequence of conditions (atomic property formulas). In INUS, it is a single condition. This discrepancy is because I take cause to be the entire minimally sufficient set of conditions for the effect, while in INUS, a cause is a single element of the set. I do this to align the theory better with CP to make comparison easier. There is no significant conceptual difference.

4.3 Semantics

The semantics provides the definition of truth in the logic. Truth is a relationship between (well-formed⁵) sentences and models. The semantics tells us exactly which sentences are true and which are false in each model. Following convention, I use \models as the symbol for the truth relation, and write $\mathbb{U} \models \underline{\sigma}$ to denote that sentence $\underline{\sigma}$ is true in a model \mathbb{U} .

To define when a sentence is true in a model, we first need to define when a property formula is true. The truth of a property formula is not evaluated against a full model as sentences are. It is a description of the state of a system and so is evaluated against a single system of a model at a single point in time. To capture this relationship we define, for every model \mathbb{U} and time t , a binary truth relation $\models_{\mathbb{U}}^t$, and write $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\varphi}$ to denote that the property formula $\underline{\varphi}$ is true for a system u in model \mathbb{U} at time t .

For atomic property formulas the definition is as follows:

- $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{P = c_P}$ holds when $\mathcal{F}(\underline{P})(u, t) = \mathcal{V}_P(\underline{c_P})$.

⁴I omit symbols for \vee and \implies and other boolean operators, since \wedge and \neg are known to be complete.

⁵For brevity I drop this qualification for the rest of the paper.

This tells us that a system u in a model \mathbb{U} at time t satisfies the atomic property formula $\underline{P = c_P}$ exactly when the property referred to by \underline{P} in model \mathbb{U} (formally given by $\mathcal{F}(\underline{P})$) assigns to the system u at time t the value referred to by c_P in model \mathbb{U} (formally given by $\mathcal{V}_{\underline{P}}(c_P)$).

Property formulas are just boolean combinations of atomic property formulas and the semantics is defined in the standard way:

- $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\gamma_1 \wedge \gamma_2}$ holds when $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\gamma_1}$ and $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\gamma_2}$ hold.
- $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\neg\gamma}$ holds when $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\gamma}$ does not hold.

We can now provide the definition of \models . When the sentence is an unqualified causal statement the definition is as follows:

- $\mathbb{U} \models (\underline{\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n}) \text{ causes } (\underline{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m})$ holds when:
 1. *Sufficiency*: For every system u and every time t in model \mathbb{U} , whenever $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\varphi_i}$ holds for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^{t'} \underline{\theta_j}$ holds as well for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$.
 2. *Minimality*: If any of the $\underline{\varphi_i}$ are removed, sufficiency fails.
 3. *Temporality*: $t' = t + 1$.

1 and 2 follow from the minimally sufficient set definition of cause. Temporality is an added constraint and is in fact inconsistent with Mackie's view of the direction of cause. Requiring $t' = t + 1$ insists that effects follow cause in time and do so immediately. The immediacy is a constraint introduced only for simplicity and will be relaxed in future work. That causes precede effects in time is however an important part of the definition. Mackie does not believe that this should hold. He says: "it is conceivable that there should be evidence for a case of backward causation, for A being causally prior to P , whereas P was temporally prior to A ." I retain 3 since I do not see the need to allow backward causation, given that no observable phenomenon exhibits it, and especially since it makes the analysis much simpler.

For qualified causal statements, $\mathbb{U} \models \underline{\gamma} \implies (\underline{\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n}) \text{ causes } (\underline{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m})$ is defined the same way that unqualified causal statements are, except that sufficiency is replaced with qualified sufficiency.

- *Qualified Sufficiency*: For every system u and every time t in model \mathbb{U} **such that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\gamma}$ holds**, whenever $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^t \underline{\varphi_i}$ holds for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $u \models_{\mathbb{U}}^{t'} \underline{\theta_j}$ holds as well for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$.

This is a straightforward modification of the semantics of unqualified causal statements. The quantification implicit in sufficiency is restricted to only those systems where the causal field $\underline{\gamma}$ is true.

5 CM subsumes CP

In this section, I show that the interpretation of cause proposed by CP can be derived from CM. I present only a sketch of the proof here, the complete version is presented in the supplement. The proof makes two assumptions about causal relations. The first is that they are not cyclical. This assumption is made because I believe that the semantics of cyclical causal models in CP is unsatisfactory. I will present a detailed reasoning for this claim and a new semantics for cyclical models in CP that is consistent with CM in future work. The second assumption is that the causal

relations are between variables that take only a finite number of values. This is due to a limitation in the language of CM that will be removed in future work. This issue is however orthogonal to the subject of this proof.

The derivation is structured as four steps. I start with a representation of causal relations in CP. I then translate the causal claims to statements in the language of CM. I provide an interpretation for interventions, also expressed as statements in the language of CM. Finally, I show that the predictions that CP and CM make about the systems after an intervention are exactly the same.

Step 1: Causal relations in CP

To provide a sketch of the proof, I use a specific example in CP, rather than a general set of causal relations. The example I will use is the switch and two bulbs example introduced in section 2. Recall that the causal dependencies of the bulbs are represented by the equations $f_{B_1}(s) = s$ and $f_{B_2}(s) = s$, and that B_1 , B_2 , and S take values in $\{0, 1\}$.

Step 2: Translation to CM

To translate the causal claims to the language of CM, we first define the signature. The signature is given by $\mathbb{S}^b = \langle \mathcal{P}^b, \{\mathcal{C}_P^b : P \in \mathcal{P}\} \rangle$, where $\mathcal{P}^b = \{\underline{B}_1, \underline{B}_2, \underline{S}\}$ is a set of symbols for the properties representing the state of the two bulbs and the switch. $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_1}^b$, $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_2}^b$ and $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{S}}^b$ are sets of symbols that refer to the values that the properties referred to by $\underline{B}_1, \underline{B}_2$, and \underline{S} can take respectively. It is natural therefore to have $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_1}^b = \mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_2}^b = \mathcal{C}_{\underline{S}}^b = \{0, 1\}$.

Let \mathbb{L}^b be the language defined over \mathbb{S}^b . The causal claims expressed in the functions $f_{B_1}(s) = s$ and $f_{B_2}(s) = s$ can be translated into the following statements in \mathbb{L}^b :

$$\begin{array}{ll} (1) \quad \underline{(S = 0) \text{ causes } (B_1 = 0)} & (3) \quad \underline{(S = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)} \\ (2) \quad \underline{(S = 1) \text{ causes } (B_1 = 1)} & (4) \quad \underline{(S = 1) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 1)} \end{array}$$

(1) and (2) follow from $f_{B_1}(s) = s$, while (3) and (4) follow from $f_{B_2}(s) = s$.

Step 3: Interpreting interventions in CM

I use the following interpretation for interventions. An intervention on a property is a cause of that property. Further, it overrides other causes of the property.⁶ To express this interpretation in the language \mathbb{L}^b , we first need to extend the signature \mathbb{S}^b to include properties for interventions. We do this by adding, for every symbol \underline{X} in \mathcal{P} , the symbol \underline{IX} that refers to a new property that describes the state of an intervention on X . The property takes on the same values that X can take, with the addition of a new value to indicate the absence of an intervention. Let $\mathbb{S}^{b'}$ be the new signature we get by applying this to the current example. We have $\mathbb{S}^{b'} = \langle \mathcal{P}^{b'}, \{\mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_2}^{b'}, \mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_1}^{b'}, \mathcal{C}_{\underline{S}}^{b'}, \mathcal{C}_{\underline{IB}_1}^{b'}, \mathcal{C}_{\underline{IB}_2}^{b'}, \mathcal{C}_{\underline{IS}}^{b'}\} \rangle$, where $\mathcal{P}^{b'} = \{\underline{B}_1, \underline{B}_2, \underline{S}, \underline{IB}_1, \underline{IB}_2, \underline{IS}\}$, $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_1}^{b'} = \mathcal{C}_{\underline{B}_2}^{b'} = \mathcal{C}_{\underline{S}}^{b'} = \{0, 1\}$, and $\mathcal{C}_{\underline{IB}_1}^{b'} = \mathcal{C}_{\underline{IB}_2}^{b'} = \mathcal{C}_{\underline{IS}}^{b'} = \{0, 1, \text{none}\}$. Let $\mathbb{L}^{b'}$ be the language over $\mathbb{S}^{b'}$. The causal claims along with interventions can now be expressed as the following set Σ' of sentences in $\mathbb{L}^{b'}$:

$$\begin{array}{ll} (1) \quad \underline{(IB_1 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_1 = 0)} & (6) \quad \underline{(IS = 0) \text{ causes } (S = 0)} \\ (2) \quad \underline{(IB_1 = 1) \text{ causes } (B_1 = 1)} & (7) \quad \underline{(IB_1 = \text{none}) \implies (S = 0) \text{ causes } (B_1 = 0)} \\ (3) \quad \underline{(IB_2 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)} & (8) \quad \underline{(IB_1 = \text{none}) \implies (S = 1) \text{ causes } (B_1 = 1)} \\ (4) \quad \underline{(IB_2 = 1) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 1)} & (9) \quad \underline{(IB_2 = \text{none}) \implies (S = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)} \\ (5) \quad \underline{(IS = 1) \text{ causes } (S = 1)} & (10) \quad \underline{(IB_2 = \text{none}) \implies (S = 1) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 1)} \end{array}$$

⁶An intervention is therefore, strictly speaking, defined for a property *and* with respect to a set of other causes for that property. An intervention with respect to one set of causes might not be an intervention with respect to another set of causes.

The sentences 1 to 6 express that an intervention causes the value of the corresponding variable to change. The sentences 7 to 10 express that the original causes of a variable are active when no interventions are occurring on that variable.

Step 4: CP follows from CM

Now that we have represented interventions in CM we can compare the two theories directly. Given the state of a system we can ask what the two theories predict about the system after an intervention. Consider a system in which the switch is kept on. CP predicts that breaking bulb 1 will result in it going dark but that bulb 2 will still be responsive to the switch and so will still be glowing.

What does CM predict? Let $\mathbb{U}^{b'}$ be any model over $\mathbb{S}^{b'}$ such that all the statements in Σ' are true. Let u be any system in $\mathbb{U}^{b'}$ such that at time t , the switch in system u is on, formally, $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^t S = 1$. Suppose that an intervention is initiated at time t that forces bulb 1 to be dark and no other intervention is effected, formally, $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^t IB_1 = 0$, $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^t IB_2 = none$, and $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^t IS = none$.

We are interested in the values of B_1 and B_2 at time $t + 1$ (the value of S will be 1 since we are assuming the switch is kept in the on position). Since $(IB_1 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_1 = 0) \in \Sigma'$, we know that it is true in $\mathbb{U}^{b'}$. From the semantics of causation this means that since $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^t IB_1 = 0$ holds it must follow that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^{t+1} B_1 = 0$ also holds. That is, at time $t + 1$ bulb 1 will not be glowing, which is the same prediction as CP.

Also, since $(IB_2 = none) \implies (S = 1) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 1) \in \Sigma'$, we know that it is true in $\mathbb{U}^{b'}$. From the semantics of qualified causal statements this means that since $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^t IB_2 = none$ and $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^t S = 1$ hold, we can infer that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}^{b'}}^{t+1} B_2 = 1$ holds. That is, at time $t + 1$ bulb 2 will be glowing, which is the same prediction as CP.

So at time $t + 1$ the system is in the same state as predicted by CP. Note the role that sufficiency played in the derivation. The claim in CP that an intervention affects only the property intervened upon follows from sufficiency. Sufficiency tells us that every time the cause conditions hold, the effect will follow. This means that if we know that the cause conditions hold, we can safely ignore everything else, including interventions, and infer that the effect will follow. It is what gives us the freedom to consider only the state of the switch to determine the state of bulb 2, and ignore the intervention on bulb 1.

6 Using interventions to defend CM

The goal of this paper is to advance CM as the correct theory of cause. A significant step is achieved by showing that it subsumes CP, but this is not sufficient in itself. There are presumably many reductive theories that are consistent with CP, but are not satisfactory as an explanation of cause. There are outstanding objections against the INUS theory, which extend to CM, that need to be given a satisfactory response. The connection between CM and interventions shown in this paper gives us a new and powerful tool for responding to these objections. In this section I provide an example of using this approach to respond to a well-known objection.

A standard objection to CM is that the definition is too broad in that while cause implies minimal sufficiency, it is going too far to claim that *all* minimally sufficient conditions are causal. An example of this is the common cause problem expressed in the well-known *Manchester-Factory-Hooters* example [13]. For convenience, we will consider an isomorphic example already introduced above of the switch with two bulbs. The common cause problem is that it sometimes seems to follow from CM that two effects of a common cause, cause each other.

In our example, the sentence $(B_1 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)$ (and also $(B_1 = 1) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 1)$) appears to be true. The reasoning is as follows. Sufficiency is satisfied. If bulb 1 is dark, it means

that the switch is off, and so bulb 2 will also be dark. Strictly speaking, temporal precedence is not satisfied since the states of bulb 1 and bulb 2 change simultaneously. But it is easy to modify the example to handle this. We can assume that B_2 is on a time delay of one extra time step.⁷ It is easy to see that minimality is also satisfied, so $(B_1 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)$ should be true.

The problem with the reasoning is that we are not modeling the system in sufficient detail. In particular, we are not modeling interventions. After incorporating interventions into the modeling, it is clear that $(B_1 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)$ is not true, since an intervention forcing bulb 2 to glow will contradict the sufficiency requirement of the statement. But this is expected, an intervention on a property overrides other causal mechanisms by definition. The interesting question is what happens when there is no intervention on bulb 2. That is, is $(IB_2 = \text{none}) \implies (B_1 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)$ true? We can see that it is not because of what happens when an intervention on bulb 1 occurs. When bulb 1 is broken, and when the switch is on, bulb 1 will be dark ($B_1 = 0$) but bulb 2 will glow ($B_2 = 1$), contradicting sufficiency.

This resolves the initial issue, but the analysis suggests that according to CM the statement $(IB_2 = \text{none} \wedge IB_1 = \text{none}) \implies (B_1 = 0) \text{ causes } (B_2 = 0)$ is true. That is, under the condition that there are no interventions on either bulb, the state of bulb 1 causes the state of bulb 2. The truth of this statement does in fact follow from CM and is not resolved by more detailed modeling. The causal field in this statement however is very extreme. It can be said of qualified causal statements in general that a severe causal field can lead to unintuitive causal relations and we must rely on some pragmatic considerations for identifying useful causal fields. I do not provide a rigorous characterization of what a useful causal field is, but it is clear that categorically restricting the ability to interfere with other variables (which is what the field $IB_1 = \text{none}$ imposes) is too extreme. CP shows us that one of the main reasons for the usefulness of cause is its implications about invariance to manipulations, in fact to the extent that CP attempts to provide a definition based on it. Completely restricting this in the causal field is therefore too extreme.

7 Conclusion and future work

I have shown that CM, a variation of the INUS theory of cause, usually considered an alternative theory inconsistent with CP, is in fact a generalization of it. This result in combination with the fact that CM is a reductive theory makes a strong case for its adoption. I have also shown how the relationship between CM and CP can be used to invalidate perceived limitations of CM.

Having a reductive theory of cause gives us an avenue to explore many important questions for which we can now get a conclusive answer. Most exciting among them are questions related to learning. CM reduces cause to universal quantification. Learning cause is therefore reduced to learning universally quantified statements, which allows us to develop more powerful learning techniques.

Having a reductive theory of cause also allows us to evaluate some existing dogmas about cause and see if they are valid or simply arise from the incomplete view of cause used so far. One example where I believe we will have to revise our view is in the claim expressed in [2] that there exists a *hierarchy of models*—probabilistic, causal Bayesian networks, and structural equation models—that have fundamentally different expressive powers. In future work, I plan to show that the characterization of these levels and their expressive power arises only from the incomplete view of cause in CP. I also claim that the semantics of cyclical causal models in CP is unsatisfactory, and

⁷This leads to the complication that S does not cause B_2 since there are now two time steps between the cause and effect. This is a consequence of the simplistic representation of time in the model and this issue will be handled in future work. The common cause problem however is orthogonal to this.

I will apply CM to derive a new semantics for them.

Many improvements can be made to CM as well. In particular, how time is represented in the model needs development, and causes that act across longer time spans need to be considered. Systems interact with each other in the real world, but the model does not currently allow for this. Also the relationship between cause, counterfactuals, and probability has not been explicated in this paper. These are possible directions for future work.

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A Complete proof that CM subsumes CP

In this section I present a complete version of the proof sketch presented in section 5 of the main paper. I prove that CP can be derived from CM. The proof requires two assumptions about causal relations.

First, I assume that they are non-cyclical. The reason for this assumption is that I believe that the semantics of cyclical causal models in CP is unsatisfactory. I claim that the predictions of cyclical models are dependent on starting states, but this is violated by the semantics of cyclical causal relations in CP. I will present a detailed reasoning for this claim and a new semantics for cyclical models in CP that is consistent with CM in future work.

Second, I assume that the causal relations are between variables that can take only a finite number of values. This is due to a limitation in the language of CM. If the variables can take an infinite number of values, it will not be possible to translate the causal claims into a finite number of sentences in CM. This is because the language does not allow causal relations to be specified using equations for functions that can express infinite causal claims in a finite way. This limitation will be removed in future work, and is orthogonal to the relationship between CP and CM that is the subject of this proof.

The proof is structured as four steps:

1. I start with a representation of causal relations in CP.
2. I then translate the causal claims to statements in the language of CM.
3. I provide an interpretation for interventions, also expressed as statements in the language of CM.
4. I show that the predictions that CP and CM make about the systems are the same.

Step 1: Causal relations in CP

Consider the specification of a set of causal relations in CP. Let:

X_1, \dots, X_n be n variables used to analyze the system.

$R(X_i)$ be the set of values that X_i can take.

$D(X_i)$ be the set of variables that X_i is dependent on. If X_i is dependent on X_j , we say that X_j is a parent of X_i .

f_{X_i} be a function in $\prod_{X_k \in D(X_i)} R(X_k) \rightarrow R(X_i)$. If $D(X_i) = \emptyset$, then f_{X_i} is not defined.

Assume that:

$D()$ represents non-cyclical dependencies.

$R(X_i)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ is finite.

The following definitions are used for convenience. Let:

X_{pi_j} be the j^{th} parent of X_i in some fixed ordering of the parents of X_i . That is, let pi_j be the variable index of the j^{th} parent of X_i .

H_i be the set of variables in the i^{th} level of the causal hierarchy represented by $D()$.⁸ Formally, $H_0 = \{X_i : D(X_i) = \emptyset\}$, the “roots” of the hierarchy. $H_i = \{X_i : D(X_i) \subset H_0 \cup \dots \cup H_{i-1} \text{ and } D(X_i) \cap H_{i-1} \neq \emptyset\}$. That is, H_i is the set of variables whose parents are all in earlier levels and at least one parent is in the immediately preceding level.

Step 2: Translation to CM

To translate the causal claims to the language of CM, we first define the signature. The signature is given by $\mathbb{S} = \langle \mathcal{P}, \{\mathcal{C}_P : P \in \mathcal{P}\} \rangle$, where:

$\mathcal{P} = \{X_i : i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\}$ are symbols for the properties.

$\mathcal{C}_{X_i} = \{c(x_i) : x_i \in R(X_i)\}$ are constant symbols for the values the properties can take.

Here $c()$ is a *constant generating function*—a function that returns a unique element⁹ for each element in $\cup_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}} R(X_i)$. I will use \underline{cx} as a shorthand for $c(x)$.

Let \mathbb{L} be the language defined over \mathbb{S} . We will translate the causal claims in step 1 as a set Σ of sentences from \mathbb{L} . Σ is constructed as follows. For each variable X_i such that $D(X_i) \neq \emptyset$ and for each element $(x_{pi_1}, x_{pi_2}, \dots, x_{pi_l}) \in \prod_{X_k \in D(X_i)} R(X_k)$ we add the following sentence to Σ :

$$\underline{(X_{pi_1} = cx_{pi_1}, X_{pi_2} = cx_{pi_2}, \dots, X_{pi_l} = cx_{pi_l}) \text{ causes } (X_i = cx_i)}$$

where $x_i = f_{X_i}(x_{pi_1}, x_{pi_2}, \dots, x_{pi_l})$ and $l = |D(X_i)|$, the number of parents of X_i .

Step 3: Interpreting interventions in CM

Interventions are interpreted as follows. An intervention on a property is a cause of that property. Further, it overrides other causes of the property.¹⁰ To express this interpretation of interventions in the language \mathbb{L} , we first have to extend the signature \mathbb{S} to include properties for interventions. We do this by adding, for every symbol X_i in \mathcal{P} , the symbol $\underline{IX_i}$ that refers to a new property that describes the state of an intervention on X . The new property takes on the same values that X can

⁸This definition is meaningful since $D()$ is non-cyclical.

⁹It does not matter from what set the element comes from. The important property is that it is unique.

¹⁰An intervention is therefore, strictly speaking, defined for a property *and* with respect to a set of other causes for that property. An intervention with respect to one set of causes might not be an intervention with respect to another set of causes.

take, with the addition of a new value to indicate the absence of an intervention. Let \mathbb{S}' be the new signature we get by applying this to \mathbb{S} . We have $\mathbb{S}' = \langle \mathcal{P}', \{C'_P : P \in \mathcal{P}'\} \rangle$, where:

$\mathcal{P}' = \mathcal{P} \cup \{IX_i : i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\}$ are symbols for the properties along with the intervention properties.

$C'_X = C_X$ are constant symbols for the values the original properties can take.

$C'_{IX} = C_X \cup \{\text{none}\}$ are constant symbols for the values the intervention properties can take. *none* is the symbol used to indicate that no intervention has taken place.

Let \mathbb{L}' be the language defined over \mathbb{S}' . The system along with the interpretation of interventions can now be expressed as a set Σ' of sentences in \mathbb{L}' . Σ' is constructed as follows. For each variable X_i and each $x_i \in R(X_i)$ we add the following sentence to Σ' :

$$\underline{(IX_i = cx_i) \text{ causes } (X_i = cx_i)}$$

This expresses that an intervention on a property causes the value of the corresponding property to change. For each variable X_i such that $D(X_i) \neq \emptyset$ and for each element $(x_{pi_1}, x_{pi_2}, \dots, x_{pi_l}) \in \prod_{X_k \in D(X_i)} R(X_k)$ we add the sentence:

$$\underline{(IX_i = \text{none}) \implies (X_{pi_1} = cx_{pi_1}, X_{pi_2} = cx_{pi_2}, \dots, X_{pi_l} = cx_{pi_l}) \text{ causes } (X_i = cx_i)}$$

where $x_i = f_{X_i}(x_{pi_1}, x_{pi_2}, \dots, x_{pi_l})$ and $l = |D(X_i)|$, the number of parents of X_i . This expresses that the original causes of a property are active when no interventions are occurring on that property.

Step 4: CP follows from CM

Now that we have translated the causal claims in CP to a set of sentences in CM we can compare the two theories directly. Recall that the interpretation of CP consists of three parts: determinism, temporality, and response to interventions. All the three parts can be inferred from CM. Determinism and temporality are straightforward and the proof is not provided here. The interesting question is whether response to interventions can be inferred from CM.

Consider a situation where an intervention is performed on variable X_a setting it to value v_a . Let r_1, \dots, r_s be indexes of the root variables, where $s = |H_0|$, the number of root variables. Assume that the root variables have values v_{r_0}, \dots, v_{r_s} . If X_a is a root variable X_{r_j} , then we assume that $v_{r_j} = v_a$. In CP, the value of the variables after interventions is got by replacing the function for X_a with $f_{X_a}() = v_a$ (or adding the function if X_a is a root variable) and solving for the system of functions with the root variables having values v_{r_1}, \dots, v_{r_s} . That a solution exists and is unique follows from the fact that $D()$ is not cyclical. Let v_1, \dots, v_n be the unique solution to the system.

Let $\mathbb{U}' = \langle \mathcal{U}', \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{F}', \{V'_P : P \in \mathcal{P}'\} \rangle$ be any model that satisfies all the statements in Σ' . Also assume that \mathbb{U}' is such that $\mathcal{V}_{X_i}(cv_i) = \mathcal{V}_{IX_i}(cv_i)$. That is, the values that an intervention and the property the intervention is on can take are the same in \mathbb{U}' . This ensures that we are working with a model that follows our interpretations of interventions.

Let $v'_i = \mathcal{V}'_{X_i}(cv_i) = \mathcal{V}'_{IX_i}(cv_i)$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. That is, v'_i is the equivalent of v_i in the model \mathbb{U}' . It is the value that is referred to by the constant $c(v_i)$ in \mathbb{U}' .

Let $\text{none} = \mathcal{V}_{IX_i}(\text{none})$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, the value referred to by *none* in \mathbb{U}' .

Let u be any system in \mathbb{U}' and t_0 be any time such that for all $t \geq t_0$, the value of the root variables for u are $v'_{r_1}, \dots, v'_{r_s}$, the value of IX_a is v'_a , and value of IX_i is *none* for all $i \neq a$.

I prove that at any time $t \geq t_0 + j$ the value of the variables in H_j for the system u are consistent with v'_1, \dots, v'_n (the equivalent of v_1, \dots, v_n in \mathbb{U}'). It follows that when j is larger than the number of hierarchies, all the variables will have values consistent with the prediction of CP. In other words, the values of the properties of u will reach an equilibrium, and the equilibrium values will be the equivalent in \mathbb{U}' of the values predicted by CP.

The proof is by induction on j .

Base Case (j=0)

We need to show that for any time $t \geq t_0$, the value of the variables in H_0 for the system u are consistent with v'_1, \dots, v'_n . The variables in H_0 are the root variables. By assumption the values of the root variables of the system u are $v'_{r_1}, \dots, v'_{r_s}$ for all $t \geq t_0$, which is trivially consistent with v'_1, \dots, v'_n .

Induction Step

Let j be an integer greater than 0. Assume that the statement holds for $0, \dots, j - 1$. Let t_j be any time such that $t_j \geq t_0 + j$. Consider $X_m \in H_j$. We need to show that at time t_j , the value of X_m for the system u is v'_m .

The proof is split into two cases.

Case 1 (m = a): This means that X_m is X_a , the variable intervened upon. By assumption, the intervention on IX_a in the system u is maintained at v'_a for $t \geq t_0$. $j > 0$ implies that $t_j - 1 \geq t_0 + j - 1 \geq t_0$ and so this means that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}'}^{t_j-1} IX_a = cv_a$ holds. From the construction of Σ' it is clear that $(IX_i = cv_a) \text{ causes } (X_a = cv_a)$ is in Σ' . Since \mathbb{U}' satisfies all the statements in Σ' , it follows that \mathbb{U}' satisfies $(IX_i = cv_a) \text{ causes } (X_a = cv_a)$.

From the semantics of causal statements therefore we can infer that since $u \models_{\mathbb{U}'}^{t_j-1} IX_a = cv_a$ holds, it follows that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}'}^{t_j} X_a = cv_a$ holds. This means that in the system u the variable X_a takes on value v'_a at time t_j . Since $a = m$, this means that in the system u , X_m takes on value v'_m at time t_j .

Case 2 (m ≠ a): This means that X_m was not intervened upon. Let $l = |D(X_m)|$, the number of parents of m . Since v_m is the value for X_m in the solution for CP, we know that $f_{X_m}(v_{pm_1}, v_{pm_2}, \dots, v_{pm_l}) = v_m$. It follows from the construction of Σ' therefore that the following sentence

$$\underline{(IX_m = none) \implies (X_{pm_1} = cv_{pm_1}, X_{pm_2} = cv_{pm_2}, \dots, X_{pm_l} = cv_{pm_l}) \text{ causes } (X_m = cv_m)}$$

is in Σ' . Since \mathbb{U}' satisfies all the statements in Σ' it satisfies this one as well.

By assumption, the absence of an intervention on IX_m in the system u is maintained for $t \geq t_0$. $j > 0$ implies that $t_j - 1 \geq t_0 + j - 1 \geq t_0$ and so this means that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}'}^{t_j-1} IX_m = none$ holds. The parents of X_m belong to hierarchies earlier than j so we know from induction hypothesis that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}'}^{t_j-1} X_{pm_i} = cv_{pm_i}$ holds for $i \in \{1, \dots, l\}$. Since \mathbb{U}' satisfies the qualified causal statement above, it follows from the semantics that $u \models_{\mathbb{U}'}^{t_j} X_m = cv_m$ holds. This means that in the system u , the variable X_m takes on value v'_m at time t_j .

This completes the proof.

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